

DOES GREEN HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES MEDIATE THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN GREEN ENTREPRENEURIAL ORIENTATION AND SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS PERFORMANCE: EVIDENCE FROM JORDANIAN FIRM

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Abstract

Today's businesses are very worried about environmental issues because many corporate activities could harm the environment. Green Human Resources Management (GHRM) practices approaches have increased in popularity in this field. However, small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) are often less inclined to adopt environmental practices compared to large companies. Hence, anchored on the natural Resource-Based View Theory, this study aims to investigate the mediating roles of GHRM practices in the link between green entrepreneurial orientation (GEO) and Sustainable Business Performance (SBP). The comprehensive research model developed in this study is empirically tested using data garnered from 168 managers of Jordanian SMEs. Partial least square structural equation modeling is applied as the methodological technique to test all the hypothesized relationships. Results of the study indicate that GEO has a direct significant positive impact on GHRM practices but not SBP. However, through GHRM practices (mediating variable), GEO tends to have a significant impact on all SBP dimensions (environmental, financial, and social performance). This study offers fresh empirical evidence by developing a unified research model that validates the specific mediation role of GHRM practices between GEO and SBP. In the end, the theoretical and managerial implications, limitations of the current study, and future research directions have been discussed.

Keywords: Sustainable Business Performance, Green Human Resources Management Practices, and Green Entrepreneurial Orientation.

1. INTRODUCTION

As the world continues to grapple with environmental issues (Guo et al., 2020), firms in the domain of both developed and fast-growing economies have started appreciating the need to minimize their environmental impacts, satisfy stakeholder demands for green products, enhance social outcomes, and enjoy superior financial gains (Baah et al., 2020). Corporate leaders' predisposition toward identifying green opportunities (Jiang et al., 2018) and capitalizing on the perceived advantages of green strategies (Demirel et al., 2019) has led to the concept of Green Entrepreneurial Orientation (GEO). As such, GEO has become a bandwagon for industrial practitioners who seek to achieve superior sustainability performance (Soomro et al., 2020).

The newness of the GEO concept has provided a promising research direction for the academic community. Previous studies on GEO have focused on Systematic Literature

Reviews (SLR) (Gast et al., 2017), conceptualization and measurement of GEO (Covin & Wales, 2012; Wales et al., 2020), and drivers or motivators for GEO (Schlange, 2006; Font et al., 2016), with limited studies concentrating on how GEO affects all three dimensions of Sustainability Business Performance (SBP) (Ecological Performance [EP], Financial Performance [FP], and Social Performance [SP]). The scant studies on the GEO-SBP relationship have often focused on either EP or FP or a combination of both EP and FP. For instance, Okangi (2019) concentrated on how entrepreneurial orientation affects firm profitability. Ahmed et al. (2020) also explored the impact of entrepreneurial orientation on EP as well as Jiang et al. (2018), who further looked at how entrepreneurial orientation influences EP and FP. This is an indication that previous scholars have often ignored the SP dimension when exploring the SEO-SBP relationships.

Besides, the number of works dedicated to the link between GEO and performance has provided divergent perspectives. For instance, Leoncini et al. (2019) contend that GEO may not necessarily lead to financial gains and firm growth. On the other hand, Gupta and Batra (2016) revealed that entrepreneurial orientation leads to better performance. The reason for the conflicting perspectives, according to some scholars (Afum et al., 2021) is attributable to the fact that there is a missing link in the relationship between GEO and SBP. Thus, instead of proposing a simple direct effect of GEO on SBP, there is a need to explain the mechanism through which GEO affects SBP. The work of Hughes et al. (2017) has specifically called for studies to investigate the process or mechanism through which GEO influences SBP. Therefore, in this study, we investigate how GEO influences SBP through Green Human Resources Management Practices (GHRM).

Additionally, compared to developed and fast-growing economies (e.g., Italy, China, Spain, USA, etc.) where studies on GEO seem to be growing exponentially (Albhirat et al., 2023c; Criado-Gomis et al., 2020), GEO studies in emergent countries (especially those in the Middel East) is still in their infancy. Specifically, the work of Albhirat et al. (2021a) has bemoaned the negligible studies on GEO in the Jordanian context; hence called for more studies in this area. Considering the increase in the number of entrepreneurial firms (Amankwah-Amoah et al., 2019) coupled with the burgeoning nature of the green bandwagon in the Middle East, particularly within the Arabian context (Hattar, 2020; Albhirat et al., 2020a), a study in this direction is relevant for industrial practitioners.

Moreover, given the fact that entrepreneurial orientation boosts the development of new products, some scholars (Guo et al., 2020; Dayan et al., 2016) have suggested that the GEO-SBP relationship is direct. However, Afum et al. (2021); and Liu and Lee (2019) indicate that the SEO-GRPI relationship may not be necessarily direct and can better be explained via green organizational practices acting as a mechanism. As such, in this study, GHRM is treated as a possible mediator between GEO and SBP. Negligible studies have looked at how GEO serves as an antecedent for the adoption of GHRM, which, in turn, leads to SBP (Albhirat et al., 2023; Afum et al., 2021). Therefore, concentrating on Jordan provides clarity to the GEO-SBP relationship from an emergent country perspective.

This study is motivated by the following reasons. First, the majority of Jordanian entrepreneurial firms fall under the category of Small and Medium-Sized enterprises (SMEs) and the SME sector has often been tagged as the major contributor to pollution emissions despite its active role in the country's industrialization drive and economic growth (Albhirat et al., 2020b). Second, given the significant rise in stakeholder activism on environmental issues and the demand for green products, the majority of Jordanian SMEs are becoming proactive in environmental issues. Most of the Jordanian SMEs are realizing that their inclination to environmental issues and the adoption of GHRM-based initiatives, as well as the offering of green-based innovative products, is integral to not only their survival but also their SBP. Third, although the literature on how entrepreneurial orientation influences SBP is flourishing, a specific focus on GEO and how it affects all three dimensions of SBP, especially SP is scant. Furthermore, studies investigating the mediation roles of GHRM between GEO and SBP are lacking.

On this backdrop, while this study aims to investigate the interrelationships between GEO, GHRM, and SBP dimensions (EP, FP, and SP), it further places specific attention on the individual mediation role (indirect effect) of SSCM between SEO and GRPI, as well as the mediating role of GHRM between GEO and SBP dimensions (EP, FP, and SP). Thus, the study attempts to answer the following specific relevant questions:

- Q1. What are the interrelationships between GEO, GHRM, and SBP?
- Q2. Does GHRM mediate the relationship between GEO and SBP?

To provide answers to these questions, data is collected from Jordanian SMEs (an emergent economy in the Middle East) and Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) is applied as the methodological tool to test the formulated hypotheses. Theoretically, the study applies the robustness of the Natural Resource-Based View (NRBV) Theory to explain the direct and indirect effects between the variables (GEO, GHRM, and SBP) under study.

Empirical studies that emphasize the indirect evaluation are scant if not non-existent, thus leading to inadequate knowledge and analysis of the causal effects. In practice, undertaking this study is a step in the right direction for corporate leaders (managers) in emerging countries (including Jordan); in that, the outcome of the study provides practical guidance that strengthens the decision-making power of GEO-based SMEs in capitalizing on sustainable practices to produce green products and further achieve their SBP goals.

The rest of the study is structured as follows: the next part concentrates on the literature review, hypotheses formulation, and research model (Figure 1). Later, the research methods are comprehensively described. Afterward, the results and discussion about the results are presented. Finally, the conclusion, as well as theoretical and practical implications are presented. The limitations and future research directions are also provided in the final part of the study.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model containing hypotheses anchored on the NRBV theory

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

2.1 Green entrepreneurial orientation and sustainable business performance

Prior studies have provided empirical evidence suggesting that entrepreneurial orientation can bring constructive benefits to firms' SBP dimensions. For instance, after cautiously collecting data from Chinese firms, Jiang et al. (2018) disclosed that GEO positively influences FP and EP. Also, the study of Habib et al. (2020) undertaken among textile manufacturers in Bangladesh unveiled that GEO influences a firm's SBP. A case study carried out in Indonesia by Erista et al. (2020) revealed that entrepreneurial orientation (innovativeness and risk-taking dimensions) has a significant impact on performance. A replica study conducted by Okangi (2019) found entrepreneurial orientation (risk-taking, innovativeness, and proactiveness) to have a positive impact on the profitability of construction firms in Tanzania.

Firms' orientation toward green-based issues is very integral to mitigating the negative impacts of their operations on the environment (Leonidou et al., 2017). GEO-based firms may contribute to superior EP through the decrease in hazardous emissions (Xie et al., 2016) and the exploitation of new green opportunities. Thus, GEO-based firms contribute to the betterment of the natural environment by way of reducing pollutants through the use of green processes (Orazalin & Baydauletov, 2020). GEO firms are likely to rely on energy-efficient methods such as the use of solar energy, which are safer for the environment due to low emission of pollution (Lee & Sine, 2009).

After randomly sampling 725 US-based non-profit organizations (specifically in the State of New York), Coombes et al. (2011) unveiled that entrepreneurial orientation tends to enhance SP. However, the same study revealed that entrepreneurial orientation does not improve FP. Another study undertaken among higher educational institutions in Germany by Brändle et al. (2019) disclosed that an entrepreneurial firm's orientation toward risk-taking positively influences not only enterprise performance but also social and

community level performance. GEO tends to play a significant role in a firm's quest to achieve sustainable sufficiency, while concurrently developing win-win green-based strategies that ensure social legitimacy and the gaining of a superior reputation (Goldsby et al., 2018; Criado- Gomis et al., 2020). The arguments above suggest that GEO is a significant catalyst for achieving superior sustainability performance in terms of improved EP, FP, and SP. As such, the following relevant hypothesis is proposed:

H1: Green entrepreneurial orientation has a significant impact on sustainable business performance.

2.2 Green Entrepreneurial Orientation and Green Human Resource Management Practices

GEO plays a pivotal role in shaping the adoption and implementation of GHRM practices within organizations (Huo et al., 2020). A strong GEO fosters a culture of environmental consciousness and innovation, driving businesses to prioritize sustainability in all aspects of operations (Cheema et al., 2015). This orientation encourages proactive initiatives aimed at reducing environmental impacts and promoting resource efficiency. In this context, GHRM practices become essential tools for realizing green objectives (Wen et al., 2022). Organizations with a high GEO are more likely to integrate green principles into their HRM strategies, such as incorporating environmental criteria into recruitment and selection processes, providing training and development programs focused on sustainability, and incentivizing green behavior among employees (Huo et al., 2020). Moreover, a strong alignment between GEO and GHRM practices can enhance organizational legitimacy and competitive advantage by demonstrating a commitment to environmental stewardship and social responsibility (Wen et al., 2022).

Furthermore, the influence of GEO on GHRM practices extends beyond internal operations to external stakeholders and supply chains (Hattar, 2020). Organizations with a green entrepreneurial orientation are inclined to collaborate with environmentally conscious suppliers and partners, fostering a network of like-minded entities committed to sustainable practices (Albhirat et al., 2023b). This collaboration enables the adoption of green supply chain management principles, wherein suppliers are selected based on their environmental performance, and joint efforts are made to reduce carbon footprints and waste throughout the supply chain (Huo et al., 2020). Additionally, a strong GEO encourages organizations to engage with communities and policymakers to advocate for environmental regulations and initiatives that support sustainability efforts. Through these channels, GHRM practices are reinforced and amplified, creating a synergistic relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and green HRM that drives organizational sustainability and resilience in the face of environmental challenges (Papademetriou et al., 2023; Wen et al., 2022). As such, the following relevant hypothesis is proposed:

H2: Green entrepreneurial orientation has a significant impact on Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) practices

2.3 Green Human Resource Management Practices and Sustainable Business Performance

It is recognized that considering greener actions in every step of HRM tasks is vital, since HRM practices support the implementation and maintenance of an environmental management system, thereby assisting a company in achieving a better EP (Jabbour & Santos, 2008b). GHRM plays an essential part in the spread and greening of firms in an effective way (Nejati et al., 2017). In addition to the obvious benefits to the environment, the implementation of green initiatives increases a company's appeal and leads to talent retention, making GHRM a crucial area of business management (Patel, 2014). Previous literature on HRM generally concentrated on the effect of individual practices on the performance of firms, rather than on a bundle of practices (Combs et al., 2006). Renwick et al. (2013) hypothesized that GHRM practices may have greater effects on environmental and organizational performance if they were jointly implemented. In line with this view, recent GHRM literature has primarily revolved around the impact of GHRM practices on the organizational performance of bundles (Longoni et al., 2016; Renwick et al., 2013). According to Russo and Fouts (1997), the RBV is capable of differentiating the resources utilized by organizations. This is believed to affect an organization's EP and ultimately improve its FP (Solovida et al., 2017). Thus, by understanding GHRM practices, organisations can improve their EP in a sustainable manner (Arulrajah et al., 2015).

In the case of SP, it is clearly important for organizations to ensure that their production operations include social activities, which can enhance the effects of plant actions on both internal communities (i.e. staff) and external communities (i.e. customers and suppliers) (Pullman et al., 2009). In addition, there is evidence to show that organizations which had adopted GHRM practices were found to significantly contribute to the living conditions of their employees, in addition to satisfying their environmental needs. The consequence was an overall positive effect on the FP of the company and on the welfare of employees (Renwick et al., 2013); Mandip (2012) also affirms that employee health and general welfare benefitted from very positive effects via their company's adoption of GHRM practices and policies. As such, the following relevant hypothesis is proposed:

H3: Green Human Resource Management Practices has a significant impact on Sustainable Business Performance

2.4 GHRM mediated effect on green entrepreneurial orientation-sustainable business performance relationship

GHRM practices serve as a crucial mediator in the relationship between GEO and SBP. GHRM practices act as the bridge that translates the environmental commitment and innovation fostered by a strong GEO into tangible organizational outcomes. Through initiatives such as green recruitment and selection processes, environmentally focused training and development programs, and incentives for sustainable behavior, GHRM practices embed green principles into the organizational culture. By aligning human resource strategies with environmental goals, GHRM practices enable employees to internalize sustainability values, leading to enhanced employee engagement,

productivity, and commitment to green objectives. Human Resources (HR) is the backbone of every organization (Khan et al., 2013, p. 179). Entrepreneurial HR are the HR managers who embrace entrepreneurial thinking and push themselves to take risks and to be innovative (Medcof & Song, 2013). Most entrepreneurial firms' HR managers understand the overall business context; hence, they play a key role in operationalizing responsibilities, team organization, training, performance indicators, teamwork, and relationships (Menon, 2012). Thus, GHRM catalyzes translating the strategic intent of GEO into actionable practices that drive SBP (Longoni et al., 2016).

Moreover, GHRM practices facilitate the development of human capital capabilities necessary for implementing sustainability initiatives effectively (Malik et al., 2023). Organizations with a strong GEO invest in building the skills and competencies required for employees to innovate and adapt to changing environmental demands (Muangmee et al., 2021). Through training programs focused on sustainability, employees gain the knowledge and expertise to identify opportunities for eco-friendly practices, improve efficiency, and develop green products or services (Malik et al., 2023). GHRM practices also foster a culture of continuous learning and improvement, encouraging employees to stay updated on emerging environmental trends and technologies (Solovida et al., 2017). As a result, organizations can capitalize on their human capital to drive innovation and differentiation in the marketplace, ultimately enhancing SBP (Al-Swidi et al., 2024).

Furthermore, GHRM practices contribute to sustainable business performance by fostering employee well-being and satisfaction (Malik et al., 2023). A strong emphasis on employee welfare, health, and work-life balance within GHRM initiatives promotes a supportive and inclusive work environment. Employees who feel valued and supported by their organization are more likely to be motivated and committed to achieving sustainability goals (Nejati et al., 2017). Additionally, GHRM practices that prioritize employee health and safety contribute to reducing environmental risks and liabilities, thereby safeguarding the organization's reputation and financial performance (Malik et al., 2023; Hattar, 2020). By nurturing a workforce that is engaged, healthy, and committed to sustainability, GHRM practices play a pivotal role in driving long-term organizational success and SBP in alignment with the principles of GEO. Consequently, we propose that:

H4: Green Human Resource Management Practices mediate the relationship between green entrepreneurial orientation and sustainable business performance.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

3.1 Sample and data collection

The study was predictive and relied on data obtained from Jordanian SMEs. To arrive at the sampling frame, the research team initially obtained information from the databases of the Amman Chamber of Commerce (ACM) in Jordan. The information from the databases helped the research team to make initial contact via email with about 280 SMEs. The research team ensured that the contacted firms were familiar with

environmental issues and had implemented GHRM practices. After the initial contact, only 168 SMEs confirmed their willingness to be included in the study. Consequently, in addition to a cover letter, the developed research instruments (questionnaires) were administered to the participating SMEs, with their respective top executives (managers) being the targeted respondents. Managers were mainly targeted because of their familiarity with environmental management. About three rounds of follow-ups through email and WhatsApp reminders were made to the participants. In total, 133 questionnaires were received at the end of the data collection period, which represents an effective response rate of 79.1%. On average, the respondents for the study have been working for their firms for over ten years. The summarized profile (demographic characteristics) of the respondents is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Profile of respondents

Category	Frequency	Percentage
The industry in which your organization belongs		
Food	73	54.8
Furniture & Kitchens	19	14.2
Metal	8	6.0
Paper (Printing & packaging)	13	10.0
Leather	4	3.0
Chemical	16	12.0
Qualification		
Director/Owner/General Manager	52	39.0
HR Manager	56	42.1
Operations Manager	11	8.3
Others	14	10.6
Number of employees		
Between 6 to 20 employees (Small)	93	70.0
Between 21 to 100 employees (Medium)	40	30.0

Note: Each value is rounded up to the integer.

3.2 Measures and questionnaire design

All items related to the constructs were measured on a 5-point Likert-scale, with 1=strongly agree to 5=strongly disagree. The items were gleaned from the extant literature review and prior validated scales. The opinion of academic professionals and industrial experts was sought before the final draft of the questionnaire. Also, a pilot test among 50 SMEs was carried out. The feedback from the pilot test and expert opinion ensured that redundant items were removed and ambiguous questions were modified. This helped to improve the content validity of the research instrument. GEO is operationalized as a firm-level strategic orientation that indicates the inclination of firms to accept methods toward the attainment of sustainable development via consciously integrating environmental and social aspects in business models and the recognition and exploitation of green opportunities for environmental protection, economic prosperity, and social gains. Five items were used to measure GEO.

GHRM practices connote the integration of environmentally sound, socially beneficial, and commercially viable initiatives or practices into a firm's entire human resources actions, ranging from green ability, green motivation, and green opportunity. In this study, nine items were used to measure GHRM practices. SBP captures EP (constructive impact of an organization's operations and the achievement of environmental targets), FP (value-creation ability of firms based on financial metrics), and SP (a performance that promotes employee well-being and how firms translate their social targets into reality). In all, nine items were used to measure SBP. It is very imperative to indicate that items that loaded significantly lower than the tolerable thresholds were removed from the model as recommended by Hair et al. (2019). Table 2 presents the construct description and its related sources, item loadings, and descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) of the items.

3.3 non-response bias and common method bias

To inspect the potential for non-response bias (NRB), the early respondents were compared with late respondents through the computation of a t-test (Armstrong & Overton, 1977). The t-test result suggested that there is no significant difference between the two groups (early respondents and late respondents). Hence, it can be confirmed that NRB did not affect the data. Besides, an ex-post analysis was conducted to test for the possibility of common method biasness (CMB) in the data.

The single common factor analysis of all the items indicates only 41.11% variance, which is lower than the upper tolerable threshold of 50% and was explained by a single component factor, thus, confirming that CMB is a negligible issue in this study. More so, surveying top executives (managers) who are well-informed about environmental issues helped to mitigate the possible dangers of CMB in this study.

3.4 Data analysis

3.4.1 Measurement Model Evaluation

Partial least square (PLS) structural equation modelling was applied as the methodological technique for the study. Using PLS ensures that a two-step approach is followed, which are measurement model evaluation and structural model evaluation. The measurement model evaluated the construct reliabilities, convergent validity, and discriminant validity.

Construct reliabilities were assessed via Cronbach's alpha (CA) and composite reliability (CR). The CA values (0.701–0.843) and CR values (0.797–0.890) exceeded the tolerable limits of ≥ 0.70 and ≥ 0.60 , respectively. The convergent validity was evaluated through average variance extracted (AVE). The AVE values (0.525– 0.649) exceeded the tolerable limit of >0.5 .

Table 3 presents the CA, CR, and AVE. Besides, the Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio was considered in evaluating discriminant validity. The result presented in Table 4 suggests that the HTMT values met the tolerable cut-off point of <0.9 .

Table 3: Construct reliability and convergent validity

Constructs	CA \geq 0.70	CR \geq 0.60	AVE $>$ 0.5
GEO	0.831	0.801	0.59
GHRM Practices	0.824	0.813	0.65
SBP	0.799	0.789	0.54

Note: GEO= Green Entrepreneurial Orientation, GHR= Green Human Resource Management Practices, SBP= Sustainable Business Performance, CA= Cronbach's Alpha, CR= Composite Reliability, AVE= Average variance Extracted.

Table 4: HTMT Ratio <0.9

Constructs	GEO	SBP	GHRM practices
GEO			
SBP	0.699		
GHRM Practices	0.699	0.699	

Note: GEO= Green Entrepreneurial Orientation, GHR= Green Human Resource Management Practices, and SBP= Sustainable Business Performance.

3.4.2 Structural Model Evaluation

Structural model evaluation was the next stage in the application of PLS as the methodological technique in this study. The model's explanatory power based on variance explained (R^2), Stone–Geisser criterion for predictive relevance (Q^2), effect size (f^2) computation, and multicollinearity determination were all considered for the evaluation of the structural model. The results from Table 5 depict that the structural model explains 50.3% of the variance in SBP and 45.4% of the variance in GHRM practices. Again, the results from the blindfolding procedure in estimating Q^2 depict that the model achieved predictive relevance: SBP ($Q^2 = 0.241$) and GHRM practices ($Q^2 = 0.275$).

Besides, f^2 was computed to find out if the exogenous construct contributed substantially to the endogenous constructs. The f^2 tolerable limits according to Benitez et al. (2020) are $0.02 \leq f^2 \leq 0.150$ (small effect), $0.15 \leq f^2 \leq 0.35$ (moderate effect), and $f^2 \geq 0.35$ (large effect size). Table 5 depicts that GEO small affects GHRM practices ($f^2 = 0.165$). On the other hand, GHRM practices have a moderate effect on SBP ($f^2 = 0.249$).

Finally, multicollinearity was verified through the variance inflation factor (VIF). The tolerable limit for VIF estimates is <3.3 and according to Table 5, the VIF estimates ($2.001 \leq VIF \leq 2.063$) limit is satisfied. Given the results from Table 5, it can be concluded that the structural model achieved superior predictive accuracy and relevance, and there were no multicollinearity issues.

Table 5: Structural Model

Constructs	R^2	Adjusted R^2	Q^2	f^2	VIF < 3.3
SBP	0.503	0.498	0.241	0.249 (moderate effect)	2.063
GHRM practices	0.454	0.448	0.275	0.165 (small effect)	2.001

Note: GHR= Green Human Resource Management Practices and SBP= Sustainable Business Performance.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Direct and indirect effects

As aforementioned, PLS was applied as the methodological tool to test all the hypotheses. In achieving this, a bootstrapping procedure with 5,000 re-samples was performed. The outcome of the bootstrapping suggests that, apart from H1b, all the other hypothesized relationships were supported. Thus, the results from Table 6 indicate that GEO has a significant positive impact on GHRM practices ($b = 0.157$, $t = 3.419$, $p\text{-value} = 0.001$). Similarly, GHRM practices have a significant positive impact on SBP ($b = 0.288$, $t = 4.355$, $p\text{-value} = 0.000$). However, GEO has no significant effect on SBP ($b = 0.084$, $t = 1.097$, $p\text{-value} = 0.139$). This connotes that H2 and H3 were supported but H1 was not supported.

The current result regarding the impact of GEO on SBP seems to be inconsistent with the work of Okangi (2019), where entrepreneurial orientation was found to positively influence firm SBP. The possible reason for the insignificant impact of GEO on SBP unveiled in this study could stem from the fact that firms in emerging countries such as Jordan may engage in high-risk behaviors such as investing in sustainable practices that have uncertain returns, especially in the short-run. A significant spending on sustainable practices may exert pressure on the short-term finances of GEO-based firms, thus affecting their SBP. Despite this result, it is important to emphasize that GEO-based firms are likely to be guaranteed long-term financial benefits when they invest in environmentally sound practices.

As displayed in Table 6, the relationships between GHRM practices and SBP were positive, and this result seems to be consistent with the work of Zaid et al. (2018). It is obvious that the results of this thorough study enable a deeper understanding of how the ethical obligations of business organisations toward the natural environment can be managed successfully. This study explores in some detail the efficiency of green management, including various organizational functions about components of SBP (i.e. EP, FP, and SP). The results reveal a positive relationship between GHRM practices and SBP (supporting H3), with the likely explanation being that the successful dissemination of environmental ideologies and standards via GHRM practices fosters the environmental management-based motivations and skills of employees. Opportunities are thereby created for employees to properly participate in the environmental development of their organization (Cantor et al., 2012; Zaid et al., 2018). A positive relationship also explains that economic value is added to a company if it has an inspired and dedicated workforce (Weber, 2008; Zaid et al., 2018). In addition, a positive relationship connotes that implementing green practices brings the benefits of reduced costs, greater sustainability, and a renewed focus on corporate social responsibility, resulting in enhancing the reputation of the company and improving community health and safety (Vyas, 2016; Zaid et al., 2018). The bootstrapping approach was further employed to test for the possible mediation effects: the mediation effect of GHRM practices in the relationship between GEO and SBP (EP, FP, and SP). The mediation procedure proposed by Huo et al. (2015) was applied to determine the presence of partial mediation or full mediation. This

mediation analysis ensures that the estimates (path coefficients and related significance levels) of direct effects and indirect effects are compared. The mediation analysis suggests that the mediation hypothesis (H4) was supported. The mediation analysis indicates that GHRM practices play a full mediation role between GEO and SBP ($b = 0.182$, $t = 4.285$, $p\text{-value} = 0.000$).

Table 6: Direct effects and indirect effects

Hypotheses	Path	Beta	T-Values	p-values	Decision
<i>A. Direct Effect</i>					
H1	GEO => SBP	0.084	1.097	0.139	Rejected
H2	GEO => GHRM	0.157	3.419	0.001	Supported
H3	GHRM => SBP	0.288	4.355	0.000	Supported
<i>B. Indirect Effect</i>					
H4	GEO => GHRM => SBP	0.182	4.285	0.000	Supported (full mediation)

5. CONCLUSION

Research on GEO has flourished rapidly in recent times, especially in developed countries. However, little empirical evidence regarding GEO has surfaced in emergent countries such as Jordan. GEO and the issues of sustainability are in a promising stage among Jordanian SMEs. Also, there are negligible empirical studies on GHRM practices as a missing mechanism through which GEO influences SBP. Likewise, how GEO influences SBP dimensions (EP, FP, and SP) through GHRM practices has rarely been discussed in the literature. This study, therefore was carried out to investigate the interrelationships between GEO, GHRM practices, and SBP dimensions (EP, FP, and SP). The study further places specific attention on the mediation role (indirect effect) of GHRM practices between GEO and SBP dimensions (EP, FP, and SP) and managed to conclude that GEO has a significant impact on GHRM practices but not SBP. Also, it suggests that GEO reinforces the adoption of GHRM practices. Again, GEO serves as a significant precursor for GHRM practices. Moreover, this study concludes that SMEs' implementation of GHRM practices will spur SBP, and GHRM practices lead to significant improvement in SMEs' SBP. Nonetheless, it was found that GHRM practices provide an explanatory link between GEO and SBP. The conclusion regarding the GEO-SBP relationship is also better explained through GHRM practices. The theoretical and practical implications were also expressed in the study.

5.1 Theoretical implications

This study makes noteworthy contributions to theoretical development in many ways. First, this study comprehensively develops a unified research model anchored on the NRBV Theory in contributing to a better understanding of the interrelationships between GEO, GHRM practices, and SBP (EP, FP, and SP). The applicability of the NRBV Theory is confirmed in this study. Second, this study adds to the rich spectrum of works on green entrepreneurship and environmental management by explaining how GEO influences all the dimensions of SBP, especially given the call for more studies on the relationship

between SEO and SP. Third, this study offers a significant contribution by responding to the call for studies on how SEO drives the adoption of sustainable supply chain management and the introduction of green-based innovative products. Finally, and most importantly, this study offers fresh empirical evidence by confirming the specific mediation role of GHRM practices between GEO and SBP dimensions (EP, FP, and SP). Establishing the mediation effects has seldom been considered by previous scholars.

5.2 Practical implications

The outcome of this study provides germane implications for managers (practitioners) and key policy decision-makers (government), particularly SME managers in emerging economies. The results provide SME managers insights into the significant role of GEO. Thus, the study informs SME managers that GEO serves as a significant conduit for achieving strong environmental, economic, and social outcomes. This will help SME managers in emerging markets to focus on GEO development and strengthen their GEO posture to gain satisfactory outcomes in terms of protecting the environment and improving social wellbeing. Again, although the study suggests that GEO alone may not be sufficient to influence SBP, this should not discourage SMEs' managers because GEO that fosters the adoption of GHRM practices, will lead to superior SBP. In particular, SMEs in emerging markets should recognize the relevance and value of GEO by implementing GHRM practices -based initiatives so as to guarantee SBP superiority.

Moreover, SMEs managers are implored to adopt a proactive management philosophy that is typified by a sustainable entrepreneurial posture that supports GHRM practices. Thus, GEO-based firms can use the implementation of sustainable practices as effective mechanisms to optimize their commitment to safeguarding the natural environment, improve financial gains, and attain SP improvement. Finally, this study presents an important milestone framework for the Jordanian government to support SMEs that develop a green entrepreneurship posture. Thus, SMEs that exhibit a proclivity toward environmental issues and apply sustainable practices should be strengthened and supported by way of economic incentives (e.g. subsidies, tax holidays, etc.) and the development of robust environmental laws. This will enable SMEs, especially those in the early stages of their existence, to achieve the desired outcomes in their SBP pursuit.

5.3 Limitations and Future Research Directions

Regardless of the significant theoretical development and practical implications of this study, certain shortcomings provide opportunities for future studies. First, data for the study is garnered from SMEs in the Jordanian context, depicting that the sample frame was from a single country. The authors, therefore, suggest that care should be taken when making generalizations. Future studies can expand the study to other geographical settings to draw confirmatory or contradictory conclusions to this study. Second, this study only investigated GHRM practices as a mediating variable in the GEO-SBP relationship. To extend this study, future studies may consider other relevant potential mediators or moderators. This will help provide additional valuable insights that may clarify the link between GEO and SBP. Third, although GEO and GHRM practices have various

dimensions, this study measured the two variables compositely. This presents an opportunity for future studies to consider the dimensions separately in a complex model. Fourth, CMB may still exist in the study even though the authors took several measures to detect the potential danger for CMB.

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Appendix A

Constructs	Measures	Sources
GEO	In general, our firm favors a strong emphasis on green practices, such as R&D, technological leadership, and innovation.	Jiang et al. (2018)
	When facing uncertainty, we typically adopt a proactive posture in order to catch potential green opportunities.	
	In dealing with competitors, we typically initiate green actions that competitors respond to.	
	Our firm favors a tendency to be a leader and always introduces green products, services, or technology first.	
	In dealing with competitors, we typically adopt a competitive ‘undo-the-competitors’ posture.	
GHRM practices	The organization prefers to recruit employees that have knowledge about the environment.	Mousa and Othman (2020)
	Employee selection takes environmental motivation into account.	
	The recruitment message includes organisations’ environmental values in job advertisement.	

	Job seekers are attracted by the environmental image and policies of the organisation.	
	The job description includes the Job's environmental aspects.	
	Training programs about environment are provided to large-scale individuals in the organisation.	
	In general, staff are satisfied with the organisation's green training.	
	Topics offered through green training are modern and suitable for the institution's activities.	
	The organisation provides formal environmental training programs for employees to increase their ability to promote them.	
SBP	Reduction of smell/odor emissions and solid waste.	Afum et al. (2021)
	Decreased energy consumption considering the volume of production.	
	Minimizes the environmental impact of the firm's activities.	
	Increased profits	
	Increase market share	
	Increased return on investment	
	Improved living quality of surrounding community	
	Decrease in rate of consumer complaints	
	Improved workers' occupational health and safety	

Note: GEO= Green Entrepreneurial Orientation, GHR= Green Human Resource Management Practices, SBP= Sustainable Business Performance.